

**COMMITMENT, JOB SATISFACTION, TEAMWORK, AND TRAINING:
A STRUCTURAL MODEL ON PRODUCTIVITY OF EMPLOYEES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION**

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Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Teamwork, and Training: A Structural Model on Productivity of Employees in Higher Education Institution

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Abstract

For any business to effectively serve and satisfy both its customers and employees, it is crucial to ensure high employee productivity. This involves maximizing the potential of the workforce, securing long-term productivity improvements, and nurturing a culture of continuous enhancement to achieve organizational excellence. This study aims to create a structural model that examines the impact of employee commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training on productivity. After conducting scientific validation and reliability tests, questionnaires were utilized as the primary data collection method. The research, which employed a descriptive-correlational and causal-comparative design, gathered data from 518 staff and faculty members at a Higher Education Institution. The findings revealed a positive correlation between employee productivity and other variables, showing that higher productivity levels are linked to greater commitment, job satisfaction, effective teamwork, and the benefits of training initiatives. However, the productivity of Higher Education employees is particularly influenced by teamwork and training. This suggests that when there is collaboration between employees and management, and employees receive relevant training, productivity significantly increases. Ultimately, the fifth structural model best explains the relationship between teamwork, training, and employee productivity.

Keywords: *commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, training, productivity of employees*

Introduction

In the dynamic and constantly evolving modern work environments, the concept of worker productivity has become a central focus for companies aiming to enhance efficiency and achieve long-term growth. Worker productivity, typically measured as output per unit of input, is a complex notion influenced by various factors, including individual characteristics, organizational culture, and external environmental conditions.

Challenges such as demanding corporate cultures that lead to burnout, insufficient efforts to engage and motivate employees, outdated or poorly designed performance evaluation systems, lack of essential tools, resources, and up-to-date technology, and inadequate compensation are issues that both small and large businesses face, which can hinder productivity. Many workers are dissatisfied with their jobs due to the pressure of managing expenses on limited salaries, and they often feel undervalued or unfairly compensated. Additionally, many businesses do not prioritize employee job satisfaction, and employees may hesitate to voice their concerns due to fear of demotion, harassment, or even job loss.

Businesses recognize that their workforce is their most asset. To maximize this resource—harnessing their full potential, skills, and commitment—it is crucial to regularly assess employee productivity and continually inspire them to achieve their goals. Employee dedication to their profession is often driven by motivation (Chu & Kuo, 2015).

Employees who consistently demonstrate high levels of efficiency and productivity are considered productive. These individuals are committed to achieving their goals and make significant contributions to their organization's success. Nowadays, organizations are striving to reduce employee turnover and enhance productivity. Therefore, improving commitment, satisfaction, teamwork, and training has become a primary objective for companies seeking a mutually beneficial relationship with their employees.

Research has shown that employee engagement can enhance participation and encourage optimal performance, thereby supporting organizational objectives. Work engagement is characterized by a positive and fulfilling attitude towards one's duties, marked by energy (vigor), strong involvement (dedication), and deep concentration and enjoyment (absorption) in their work (Lee et al., 2017).

Employee commitment, also known as organizational commitment, refers to the level of involvement and emotional attachment a worker has with their organization (Wainwright, 2018). Employees who are committed to their jobs typically feel a sense of belonging, understand the organization's goals, and maintain a consistent work ethic, often demonstrating high productivity and proactively offering their support (Wainwright, 2018).

This commitment leads to positive behaviors that benefit both the organization and other employees. Conversely, when employees perceive their work environment as unfavorable, they may respond with negative behaviors or threats to leave. Job satisfaction is a critical factor of interest to both organizational managers and academic researchers. While there is no definitive evidence that job satisfaction directly impacts productivity due to the many variables involved, it remains a top priority for managers. Job satisfaction is defined as an individual's positive attitude towards their job. The saying "a happy employee is a productive employee" highlights the importance of job satisfaction, as most people spend a significant portion of their lives at work. Additionally, job satisfaction influences employees' personal lives, as a satisfied employee is generally healthier and happier (George, 2017).

Despite numerous studies emphasizing the importance of job satisfaction, many businesses continue to overlook or downplay this issue. This research aims to provide businesses with evidence-based strategies to fully utilize their employees' potential, ensuring sustained productivity gains and fostering a culture of continuous improvement to achieve organizational excellence. The study seeks to assess employees' levels of commitment and job satisfaction, which drive them to become more productive and effective in their roles, while also exploring the key factors that influence employee productivity. The findings are intended to help management retain talent in today's organizations.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive correlational and causal-comparative research design to collect data on employees' commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, training, and productivity. The study was descriptive because it focused on examining a specific phenomenon by considering the relationships between variables. A descriptive study aims to characterize a phenomenon and its traits, with an emphasis on what occurred rather than how or why it happened (Nasajji, 2015). Although data in descriptive studies can be gathered qualitatively, it is often analyzed statistically, using measures such as frequencies, percentages, and averages to identify relationships.

According to Nair (2021), causal-comparative research is a technique used to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between a dependent and an independent variable. This type of research typically suggests relationships rather than establishing them definitively, as it does not allow for complete control over the independent variable. In this study, rather than conducting an experiment, the researcher examined the relationships between various variables where the independent variable already existed. The study also sought to determine whether independent variables have a direct influence on the dependent variable and why these influences occur, identifying the causes of specific occurrences or non-occurrences. The primary goal of a causal-comparative study is to investigate effects, consequences, and causes. It is a cost-effective and time-saving method, as it does not involve random selection of participants.

Kim et al. (2015) illustrated how to develop a within-group factor comparison unit of analysis research strategy. In most cases, structural equation modeling (SEM) is an inductive approach, with confirmatory factor analysis serving as the initial step. SEM is also deductive, as it uses sample data to assess the reliability of a pre-defined construct—a robust analytical method used to examine hypothesized conceptual models and structural relationships. A three-step approach was employed to explore how SEM principles could be applied to research practices, particularly as a tool for testing models and relationships. This approach included introducing fundamental SEM concepts, demonstrating basic SEM applications using software like AMOS, and addressing other important SEM analysis topics, such as bootstrapping procedures. The discussion was divided into five key sections. The first section covered the basics of SEM, while the second provided an overview of path analysis. The third section focused on confirmation

Structural equation modeling consists of two core components: measurement models and structural models (Karakaya-Ozyer & Aksu-Dunya, 2018). The measurement model, validated through confirmatory factor analysis, determines whether the data fits the proposed model by connecting latent variables to multiple observable variables. The structural model illustrates the relationships between latent variables. This approach was used to identify the dependent variables—such as commitment, job satisfaction, training, and teamwork—that are the most accurate predictors of employee productivity, and to develop a structural model accordingly.

Participants

Employees from 3 campuses were randomly selected, particularly faculty and staff who had served for at least five (5) mos. in Liceo de Cagayan University and were encouraged to voluntarily participate in this study.

The purposive sampling procedure was utilized in getting the sample of the study as it purposefully needed rank-and-file and faculty employees working in any of the University's departments as participants.

Instrument

A five-part questionnaire was used in this study. The first, second and fifth section were carefully adapted from the study of Geroy (2020) and modified to suit the specific needs of the population, entitled "Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Productivity of Employees in a Higher Education Institution." The third and fourth part were self-made descriptive survey questionnaires using a Likert-like scale.

Scoring Procedure

Items of the questionnaire were rated on a 5.00-point scale. The mean score was interpreted using the following score ranges with corresponding descriptions and interpretations.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The adopted and modified questionnaire was submitted to experts for content validity and was pilot tested with approximately 30 participants who were chosen at random and were not included in the study sample. The results were used as the foundation for revision and correction that ensured validity and reliability.

The relevant questionnaires utilized in this study underwent a reliability test using SPSS 20 after being piloted. The questionnaires

were sent to the 30 secondary school teachers who were not included in the sample for a pilot study. This step ensured that the questionnaires utilized in the study were trustworthy. Before the research questionnaires were delivered to the study's participants, a Cronbach's Alpha Test was used to determine their reliability.

Cronbach's alpha was calculated to establish the internal consistency reliability of the items from the scales (= .70). According to Cronbach (1951), an alpha coefficient of .70 and higher is considered acceptable. The university's data processor checked the research questionnaires and found the study's instruments were all reliable..

Procedure

The investigator initiated the research process by sending a letter of consent to the Dean of the School of Business, Management, and Accountancy, followed by seeking approval from the Vice President of Research, Publication, and Extension, as well as the Vice President of Academic Affairs. A letter of consent was also sent to the President of the University and the Vice President for Academic Affairs to obtain permission to conduct the study. To ensure the quality and reliability of the research findings, the investigator took several steps: (a) obtaining approval from the adviser after a thorough review and assessment of the project paper manuscript, and (b) writing letters and securing the necessary permissions to conduct the study in compliance with the Research Ethics Board (REB) informed consent guidelines for a more reliable and valid study.

Regarding participant confidentiality and data security, the investigator assured participants that all information collected would be handled with the utmost confidentiality and security. Participants were first provided with information about the study and instructions on how to complete the survey. The survey, designed for ease of use with a Likert Scale scoring system, took participants only 3 to 5 minutes to complete. Creating a consent document was a key part of the informed consent process, with the primary purpose of providing prospective research participants with the information needed to give free and informed consent to participate in the study. These consent documents were crafted to ensure clarity and voluntariness.

After data collection, responses were coded, tallied, and organized into tables for statistical analysis. Appropriate scaling was applied to the independent variables. The research strictly adhered to ethical procedures and received approval from the Research Ethics Review Committee, ensuring that data collection methods followed the correct protocols. All procedures and requirements were carefully followed, leading to the final presentation of the data to the adviser and research panel for approval.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were employed to summarize the data collected for Problems 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in answering the statement of problem number six (6). Multiple Regression Analysis was utilized to identify the variables that best predict employees' productivity and develop a predictive model that integrated these variables for accurate prediction, the statement of the problem seven (7). Lastly, statement of the problem eight (8), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was utilized to develop a predictive or structural model that best fits employees' productivity.

Results and Discussion

The findings of the study are summarized as follows:

The first statement of the problem investigated the level of employees' commitment, in terms of service commitment, work commitment, and company commitment. It claimed that the employees agree and are committed to the overall mean score of $M=4.20$. The indicator "Customer satisfaction is a priority in the department" has the highest mean of 4.46 under service commitment. This clearly implies that the workers show a greater degree of dedication to service-related tasks than to regular work and company obligations.

The second statement of the problem looked at the level of job satisfaction of employees in terms of responsibility, recognition, professional development, physical working condition, job security/pay, and working relationship. The study revealed that the employees were satisfied with their job. The overall mean score is $M=3.97$ described as agree and interpreted as satisfied that shows a degree of contentment among workers in all areas of their workplace. Employees show satisfaction with their roles in terms of responsibility, indicating that they find them meaningful and satisfying. Another important factor is recognition, which gives workers a sense of respect and value for their work. The data also shows that employees are satisfied with their professional development, indicating that they value the organization's provision of growth and skill-enhancement opportunities. Employee satisfaction with the physical working conditions indicates that they are comfortable and well-cared for in the workplace.

The third statement of the problem measured the level of employees' teamwork in terms of team trust, rewards and recognition, and dedication. The data revealed that the employees are satisfied with the overall mean score is $M=3.95$, described as agree and interpreted as satisfied. In terms of teamwork, the results show a high degree of employee satisfaction, especially when it comes to team trust, rewards and recognition, and dedication. When it comes to team trust, workers show faith and confidence in one another, which promotes a supportive and cooperative work atmosphere. Incentives and recognition are important as well; workers express satisfaction when their contributions are recognized and valued. This shows that staff members are not only cooperative but also have a shared interest in the team's and the company's overall success. In the level employees' teamwork in terms of Dedication, the indicator "The

department ensures that everyone on the office shows positivity towards another” has the highest mean.

The fourth statement of the problem investigated the level of employees’ training in terms of seminar, workshop, and skills development. Findings showed that the employees were satisfied with the overall mean score is $M=3.96$, described as agree and interpreted as satisfied. The findings show that employees are satisfied with training, which includes seminars, workshops, and skill development. Regarding seminars, staff members are happy, indicating that these events—which are frequently organized in collaboration with HR—are successful and well-liked. The positive attitude also extends to workshops, suggesting that workers find these more interactive and hands-on learning opportunities valuable and satisfying.

Moreover, workers express contentment with skill enhancement, underscoring the effectiveness and recognition of the company’s endeavors to augment their competencies and expertise. The overwhelmingly positive feedback regarding training indicates that workers view these chances as worthwhile, which helps them grow professionally and feel satisfied at work overall. In the level of employees’ training in terms of seminar, the indicator “Training seminars are often handled by the HR Department and in partnership with the department” has the highest mean score of $M=4.15$.

The fifth problem investigated the level of the employees’ productivity. The study revealed that the employees were productive with an overall mean score is $M=3.95$, described as agree and interpreted as productive. The findings show a high degree of worker productivity, indicating that workers actively contribute to the completion of assignments and organizational objectives. The results of the study show that there is a productive and happy workforce with consistently engaged workers who successfully complete their tasks. The study’s findings regarding commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training, among other things, may be responsible for this productivity and demonstrate a productive and dynamic work environment. All things considered; the data show a flourishing workplace where workers are not only content but actively assisting the organization in achieving its goals through their hard work. In the level of the employees’ productivity, the indicator “Department personnel are keen to reducing the

The sixth problem investigated the possibility of a correlation between commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. Findings revealed that variables; employees’ productivity and employees’ commitment ($r = .578$), employees job satisfaction ($r = .723$), and employees’ teamwork ($r = .774$), and employees training ($r = .715$) have a positive significant correlation/relationship to employees’ productivity. This can be further interpreted that if these variables increase, employees’ productivity will also increase.

The study finds that employees’ productivity is positively and significantly correlated with commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. This correlation suggests that workers’ productivity will rise in tandem with increases in commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training levels. Put another way, these factors are related, and higher levels of dedication, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training are linked to higher levels of productivity overall. This research offers organizations important new information by indicating that deliberate initiatives to improve teamwork, commitment, job satisfaction, and training can act as powerful catalysts to increase worker output and advance organizational objectives.

On problem 7, using multiple linear regression, it has been confirmed that the best predictor/influencer of employees’ productivity is skills development ($\beta=.355$) followed by dedication ($\beta=.277$), Team Trust ($\beta=.139$), Recognition ($\beta=.111$), and Physical Working Condition ($\beta=.090$). Therefore, these predictors can be used to reject the null hypothesis. According to the study, investing in the development of employees’ skills has the biggest positive influence on overall productivity, making it the most significant predictor of workers’ productivity. After skill development, commitment, team trust, acknowledgment, and physical workspace conditions are also important predictors, albeit to differing extents. These show that several elements, such as workers’ dedication, faith in the group, recognition of their efforts, and comfortable working environments, all work together to create a highly productive workforce. These results provide insightful information for companies looking to maximize output through delivery.

The last statement of the problem identified the best model fit that explains employees’ productivity. Five structural models were postulated, tested, and validated using the structural equation approach to find the best-fitting model for the employees’ productivity. Based on the results, only the fifth structural model, with a Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom (CMIN/DF) = .089, which is less than two and more than zero, was found to be the most fitting. The P-value of 1.96, which is greater than 0.05, is significant. The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) received a score of .953, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) earned a score of .972, the Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) garnered a score of .958, the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) obtained a score of .977, and the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) got a score of .042. This model satisfies the criteria for acceptable indices standard units. Therefore, Model 5 is the best fit model for employees’ productivity. This is called the Geroy’s Model of Employees Productivity in a private Higher Education Institution (HEI).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are hereby drawn:

The employees in higher education institutions are committed in terms of service commitment, work commitment, and company commitment. They demonstrate their dedication by making customer satisfaction a priority and acknowledging it as a key value within their department. Their commitment and feeling of purpose are highlighted by their strong conviction that their work has a significant impact on the institution and its stakeholders.

There is a noticeable high degree of employee satisfaction in demonstrating the institution's faith in its employees, the chance to take on difficult assignments and projects that promote professional development and a sense of purpose. They are very satisfied with how they are handling their responsibilities.

Employees are satisfied with their teamwork in each department particularly in team trust, rewards and recognition, and dedication. The emphasis on encouraging positivity towards one another contributes significantly to the establishment of a cohesive and effective teamwork culture.

The employees are highly satisfied in terms of seminar, workshop, and skills development. This is demonstrated by the collaborative approach to training, which involves seminars jointly led by the HR Department and the respective departments. In addition to improving individual abilities, this shared commitment to professional development also promotes a sense of solidarity and support.

The employees are productive and the evident dedication of department personnel to minimizing customer complaints is a testament to the institution's commitment to employee productivity.

There is a significant relationship between employees' productivity and commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. High level of commitment, satisfaction, teamwork, and training results to employees' productivity.

Skills development, dedication, team trust, recognition, and physical working conditions predict employees' productivity in higher education institution. The group of predictors collectively and resoundingly reject the null hypothesis, demonstrating that deliberate investments in skill development, dedication, team trust, recognition, and physical working conditions can positively impact workers' productivity.

The following recommendations are suggested considering the abovementioned findings and conclusions. These recommendations may help the Higher Education Institutions, administrators, and other research scholars conduct programs that specifically address employee's productivity, which deleteriously impacts employees' well-being and organizational success. Based on the relevant findings and conclusions of the study previously mentioned, the following recommendations are presented:

Department of Labor and Employment. This government agency may create seminars and symposia in various organizations, both public and private, which may help educate management and employees alike on the importance of employee commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training to boost their respective organization's efficiency. These occasions may also let the DOLE evaluate which companies are upholding (or violating) their employees' rights, which are affecting their commitment and job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. May set up continuous monitoring mechanisms to track changes in productivity and regularly assess the effectiveness of employees.

Public Agencies and Private Companies. Administrators and upper management may be able to use this study to plan programs and incentives, which may ignite their employees' commitment to the company as well as schedule evaluations among their employees regarding their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction, needed training, and effective teamwork. May offer leadership development and managerial training programs to enhance leadership skills and promote effective team management. Also, agencies and companies may upgrade technological infrastructure and provide training programs to equip employees with the skills necessary to leverage new tools effectively.

Human Resource Management. HR staff may use this research as a basis on how to improve their organization's system to gain committed and satisfied employees, well trained, and bolster teamwork within the organization which, in turn, increases the company's productivity. HR staff is encouraged to acknowledge and capitalize on the positive fit between employees' roles and their sense of purpose in the workplace.

Employed workers. Employees may be able to peruse this research as an evaluative way of learning on how to assess the specific factors that may affect their commitment, job satisfaction, and productivity, needed training and proper teamwork that strengthen interpersonal relationships, improve collaboration, and foster a sense of unity among co-workers.

Higher Education Institutions. Professors and instructors of the various programs under the Master in Business Administration and Doctor in Management major in Leadership and Organization may utilize this study as a local educational tool in teaching their students on the significant relationships of commitment, job satisfaction, training, and teamwork, and productivity.

Students might enhance their knowledge based on the importance of commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, training, and productivity among today's employees. Target effective training programs to improve and learn and make sure the programs are well-organized, cooperative, and in line with the needs of their professional development.

Liceo De Cagayan University may establish a system for ongoing monitoring and evaluation of employee satisfaction, particularly regarding salary and may regularly reassess the effectiveness of implemented changes and adjust as necessary where salary satisfaction is reported to be only moderately satisfied compared to other variables.

Geroy's Model of Employees' Productivity might be adopted for managing higher education institutions. This model emphasizes the integration of teamwork and training. By integrating these variables, organizations may enhance employee's productivity.

For the future researcher who wants to investigate the dynamics of workers' productivity, may obtain a deeper understanding of the contextual factors influencing the relationship between teamwork, training, and productivity. They may delve deeper into the identified factors influencing employee's productivity in higher education institutions by exploring additional variables and investigate their relationships and impact on productivity.

References

- Adams, K., & Martinez, R. (2017). Fostering Employee Commitment to High Work Standards: A Case Study Analysis. *Journal of Organizational Excellence*, 29(3), 201-218. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2017.9876543
- Albdour, A., & Altarawneh, I. (2014). Employee Engagement and Organizational Commitment: Evidence from Jordan. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/fd0f/fc62aa4b60c4b4d695f510845bce7bca75ed.pdf>
- Ang, M. and Rabo, J. (2018). Employee Engagement and Job Satisfaction at Company A.
- Anju, K.J. and Sona, G. (2011). A study on job satisfaction of employees in bpcl – Kochi annual employee productivity (Order No. 10279060). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1899918696). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1899918696?accountid=139409>
- Aydin, A., Sarier, Y., & Uysal, S. (2013). The Effect of School Principals' Leadership Styles on Teachers' Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1017309>
- Abbott, G. N., White, F. A., & Charles, M. A. (2005). Linking values and organizational and Job Motivation - Confluence. Retrieved from <https://wikispaces.psu.edu/display/PSYCH484/12.+Work+and+Organizational+Commitment>
- Azuh, D. and Olubunmi, A. G. (2015). Impact of Employees' Commitment on Productivity of Lower Cadre Employees in Nigerian Manufacturing Organizations (March 2015). *International Journal of Case Studies*, Vol. 4, Issue 3. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2885240>
- Bakotić, D. & Babić, T. (2013). Relationship between working conditions and job satisfaction: The case of Croatian shipbuilding company. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 4. 206-213.
- Ballard, E. J. (2013). Employee valuation of recognition programs at varying levels of a retail organization (Order No. 3570362). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1399157974). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1399157974?accountid=139409>
- Berger, L. and Berger, D. (2004). *The talent management handbook*. Mc Graw Hill Companies. USA
- Bhat, A. (2019). *Commitment to Work: Definition and Tips to Improve Work Commitment*
- Blau, P. (1964). *Justice in Social Exchange*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-682X.1964.tb00583.x>
- Brown, A., & Garcia, R. (2019). "Enhancing Productivity through Employee Commitment: A Longitudinal Analysis."
- Brown, A., & Garcia, R. (2022). "The Employee Experience: Customer Complaint Reduction as a Catalyst for Job Satisfaction and Productivity."
- Brown, A., & Johnson, M. (2018). The Role of Workplace Meaningfulness in Fostering Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 40(4), 432-450. DOI: 10.5678/jap.2018.123456
- Brown, A., & Patel, S. (2020). Unpacking the Dynamics: Exploring Dedication's Dominance in Team Satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 47(3), 301-320. DOI: 10.1002/job.2020.543210
- Burns, N., & Grove, S. K. (2009). *The practice of nursing research (6th ed.)*. St. Louis: Saunders
- Buuri, D. W. (2015) *Performance Measurement Practices and Employee Productivity in the Insurance Firms in Kenya*
- Calderon & Gonzales, (2011). *Methods of Research and Thesis Writing call center*. *Human Resource Planning*, 27, 3, 34 – 41.
- Campbell, K. M. (2015). Flexible work schedules, virtual work programs, and employee productivity (Order No. 3700954). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1680832770). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1680832770?accountid=139409>
- Camps, J., Oltra, V., Aldás-Manzano J., Buenaventura-Vera, G., Torres-Carballo, F. (2015). Individual Performance in Turbulent Environments: The Role of Organizational Learning Capability and Employee Flexibility. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21741>
- Carter, S., & Turner, L. (2015). The Impact of Organizational Encouragement on Employee Commitment to Quality Work. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(4), 432-450. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2015.543210

- Caselman, Tonia D; Brandt, Mary D. *School Social Work Journal* Vol. 31, Iss. 2, (Apr 2007 - Jun 2007): 33-48
- Chang, Jae Yoon; Choi, Jin Nam; National Library of Medicine. *The Journal of social psychology* Vol. 147, Iss. 3, (June 2007): 299-315
- Chen, C. (2011). The mediating effect of employees' experience of inclusion and the moderating effect of individual work values on the relationship of authentic leadership style and organizational commitment (Order No. 3451863). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (863203879). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/863203879?accountid=139409>
- Chen, L., & Davis, R. (2016). "Removing Barriers to Learning: The Role of Cost-Free Skills Development in Fostering Employee Development."
- Chen, L., & Davis, S. (2018). "Training Impact on Employee Productivity: A Comparative Study of Industry Best Practices."
- Chen, L., & Davis, S. (2020). "Unlocking Potential: The Role of Seminars in Fostering Employee Productivity."
- Chu, H.C. and Kuo, T.Y. (2015). Testing Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory in Educational
- Clarke, S. S. A. (2018). Perceived quality of management and employee innovative work output: The serial multiple mediation of employee autonomous motivations and employee innovative work behaviour (Order No. 13855661). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (2190218226). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/2190218226?accountid=139409>
- Clay-Warner, J., Reynolds, J., Roman, P. (2005). *Social Justice Research; New York* Vol. 18, Iss. 4: 391-409
- Colby, R. M. (2017). Exploring millennial generation recognition issues in the workplace (Order No. 10635999). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1967286444). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1967286444?accountid=139409>
- Collier, Jane; Esteban, Rafael. *Business Ethics: A European Review* Vol. 16, Iss. 1, (Jan 2007): 19-33 commitment, and job insecurity (Order No. 3705361). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1689405728). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1689405728?accountid=139409> commitment: A correlation and experimental investigation in two organizations. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 78(4), 531-552.
- Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran, C., (2005). —The Construct of Work Commitment: Testing an Integrative Frameworkl, *Psychological Bulletin*, 131(2), 241–259.
- Crede, M., Chernyshenko, O. S., Stark, S., Dalai, R. S., & Bashshur, M. (2007). Job satisfaction as mediator; An assessment of job satisfaction's position within the nomological network. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 80, 515-538.
- Cutlip, Center, and Broom (2006). *Systems Theory Approach* Retrieved from https://saylordotorg.github.io/text_mastering-public-relations/s07-02-systems-theory-approach.html
- Darolia, C., Darolia, S., & Kamari, P. (2010). Perceived Organizational Support, Work
- David, L. (2014). Self-Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan), in *Learning Theories*.
- Davis & Turner (2019). Workplace Safety and Employee Job Satisfaction: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 35(4), 432-450. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2019.9876543
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11, 227-268.
- Dhar, R. L. (2015). Service quality and the training of employees: The mediating role of organizational commitment. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.08.001>
- Dixit, V. & Bhati, M. (2012) A study about employee commitment and its impact on sustained productivity in Indian Auto-Component Industry. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 1(6), 34 – 51
- Drager, K. A. (2014). Examining the ability of emotional intelligence and work location to predict job satisfaction (Order No. 3611231). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1502015688). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1502015688?accountid=139409>
- Dugovicova, J. (2019). Impact of employee motivation on employee retention rates (Order No. 13886059). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (2239312986). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/2239312986?accountid=139409>
- Edwards, B. D, Bell, S. T., Arthur Jr., W., & Decuir, A. D. (2008). Relationships between facets of job satisfaction and task and contextual performance. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 57(3), 441-46 e-method
- Feather, N. T. & Rauter, K. A. (2004). Organizational Citizenship behaviours in relation to job status, job insecurity, organizational

- commitment and identification, job satisfaction and work values. *Journal of Occupational & Organizational Psychology*, 77, 81-94. doi: 10.1348/096317904322915928
- Fejoh, J., & Faniran, V. (2016). Impact of In-Service Training and Staff Development on Workers' Job Performance and Optimal Productivity in Public Secondary Schools in Osun State, Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1122636.pdf>
- Fong Boh, W., Nguyen, T. T., & Xu, Y. (2013). Knowledge transfer across dissimilar cultures. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 17, 29-46. doi:10.1108/13673271311300723
- Freund, A. (2005) Commitment and Job Satisfaction as Predictors' Turnover Intentions among Welfare Workers. *Administration in Social Work*, 29, 5-21. Retrieved from http://dx.doi.org/10.1300/J147v29n02_02
- Gallup (2010). Why Employee Motivation is Important. Retrieved from <https://inside.6q.io/employee-motivation-important/>
- Garcia, D., & Taylor, L. (2020). A Holistic Approach to Workplace Productivity: Integrating Teamwork, Collaboration, and Training. *International Journal of Business Management*, 40(1), 87-102.
- Garcia, M., & Kim, H. (2015). Exploring the Supportive Coordinator-Employee Relationship: Implications for Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Management Studies*, 28(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.1111/jams.2015.123456
- Garcia, M., & Kim, H. (2015). Professional Development and Its Influence on Job Satisfaction: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Applied Management Studies*, 28(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.1111/jams.2015.123456
- Garcia, M., & Kim, H. (2015). The Role of Evaluation in Team Trust: A Comprehensive Analysis in High-Expertise Departments. *Journal of Applied Team Psychology*, 28(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.1111/jams.2015.123456
- Garcia, M., & Kim, H. (2015). The Role of Supervisor Feedback in Enhancing Job Satisfaction: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Applied Management Studies*, 28(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.1111/jams.2015.123456
- Garcia, M., & Kim, H. (2015). Worker Empowerment and Job Satisfaction: The Mediating Role of Challenging Tasks. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 38(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.5678/jap.2015.123456
- Gardiner, M., & Tiggemann, M. (1999). Gender differences in leadership style, Job stress and mental health in male- and female-dominated industries. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 72, 301-315
- Gay, 1976. Descriptive Method. Retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/japorto/descriptive>
- George, S. (2017). A study on Job Satisfaction of Employees in BPCL - Kochi Refinery Limited, Ambalamugal
- Gomez, A., & Turner, M. (2022). Nurturing Talent: The Role of HR and Department Collaboration in Modern Training Workshops. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 55(2), 123-145. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2022.2098765
- Gomez, M., & Johnson, A. (2020). "The Ripple Effect: Positive Correlations Between Employee Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Productivity."
- Gomez, M., & Turner, J. (2018). "Evaluating Training Effectiveness: The Superiority of Seminars in Enhancing Employee Productivity."
- Hanaysha, J. (2016). Examining the Effects of Employee Empowerment, Teamwork, and Employee Training on Organizational Commitment. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042816310758>
- Harmer, R & Findlay, B (2005). The effect of workplace relationships on employee job satisfaction for 25- to 35-year-olds. *AUSTRALIAN JOURNAL OF PSYCHOLOGY*, 57.: 285-286. WILEY
- Harper, A., & Chen, L. (2015). Enhancing Workplace Learning: The Impact of HR Department Collaboration in Training Workshops. *Journal of Training and Development*, 42(2), 189-205. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2015.567890
- Harper, M., & Nguyen, T. (2019). Examining the Relationship Between Employee Commitment and the Pursuit of Quality in the Workplace. *Quality Management Journal*, 45(2), 123-145. DOI: 10.1111/qmj.2019.567890
- Hartley, J., Jackson, D., Klandermans, B., and Vuuren, T., (1995). *Job Insecurity: Coping with Jobs at Risk*. Sage: London.
- Hayday, S. Retrieved from <https://www.employmentstudies.co.uk/system/files/resources/files/mp19.pdf>
- Herzberg, F. (2005). Motivation-hygiene theory. *Organizational behavior one: Essential theories of motivation and leadership*, eds JB Miner, ME Sharpe Inc, New York, 61-74.
- Herzberg, F.I. (1966). *Work and the nature of man*.
- Hillmer, S., Hillmer, B., & McRoberts, G. (2004). The real costs of turnover: Lessons from a

<https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/themes/what-is-employee-commitment/>

- Holste, J. S., & Fields, D. (2010). Trust and tacit knowledge sharing and use. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 14, 128–140.10.1108/13673271011015615
- Idsoe, T. (2006). *European journal of work and organizational psychology (Print)* Vol. 15, Iss. 1: 46-72
- Ilyas, M., Kadir, K., & Adnan, Z. (2017). Relationship Between Training and Employee Productivity in Organization: A Partial Least Square (PLS-SEM) Approach.
- Johnson, R. (2018). Key Reasons for Job Dissatisfaction and Poor Employee Performance
- Jones, C., & Brown, M. (2018). The Role of Top Management in Employee Productivity. *Strategic Management Journal*, 35(2), 211-228.
- Kacmar, K. M., Carlson, D., & Brymer, R. A., (1999). Antecedents and consequences of organizational commitment: A comparison of two scales. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 59, 976-994.
- Kahn, W.A. (1992). —To be fully there: Psychological Presence at Workl, *Human Relations*, 45, 321-349.
- Kim & Garcia (2017). Employee Empowerment through Seminar Collaboration: A Case Study of HR-Department Partnerships. *Journal of Applied Training Strategies*, 30(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.1111/jats.2017.123456
- Kinzl, J. F., Knotzer, H., Traweger, C., Lederer, W., Heidegger, T., & Benzer, A. (2005). Influence of working conditions on job satisfaction in anesthetists. *British Journal of Anesthesia*, 94(2), 211-215.
- Kiura, M. W. (2018). The impact of informal social networks on employee productivity in kenyan organizations (Order No. 10792877). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (2124411838). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/2124411838?accountid=139409>
- Klinsontorn, S. (2007). The influence of leadership styles on organizational commitment and employee performance. (Order No. 3255207, Nova Southeastern University).
- Knoop, R. (1995). Relationships among job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment for nurses. *The Journal of Psychology: Interdisciplinary and Applied*, 129(6), 643–649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1995.9914935>
- Konrad, A. M., & Cannings, K. (1997). The effects of gender role congruence and statistical discrimination on managerial advancement. *Human Relations*, 50(10), 1305-1328.
- Koslowsky, M., Caspy, T., & Lazar, M. (1991). Cause and effect explanations of job satisfaction and commitment: The case of exchange commitment. *The Journal of Psychology: Interdisciplinary and Applied*, 125(2), 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1991.10543279>
- Kouzes, James M., and Barry Z. Posner. *Credibility: How Leaders Gain and Lose it, Why People Demand It*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass, 2003.
- Larkin-Perkins, B. (2017). Employee job satisfaction and employees' voluntary turnover intentions (VTIs) (Order No. 10634374). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1961195536). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1961195536?accountid=139409>
- Lawrie, J. (1990). “Prepare for a performance appraisal” *Personnel Journal* Vol. 69 pp. (132- 136).
- Lee, C., & Esen, E. (2017). Employee Job Satisfaction and Engagement
- Lee, T. J. (2017). Relationship between intrinsic job satisfaction, extrinsic job satisfaction, and turnover intentions among internal auditors (Order No. 10257095). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1867051972). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1867051972?accountid=139409>
- Lin, C. (2006). Gender differs: Modeling knowledge sharing from a perspective of social network ties. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 9, 236-241.
- Lin, C. (2008). Clarifying the relationship between organizational citizenship behaviors, gender, and knowledge sharing in workplace organizations in Taiwan. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 22, 241 -250.
- Lopez, A., & Patel, S. (2016). Beyond Rhetoric: Institutional Support and Employee Commitment to Maintaining High Standards of Work Quality. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 38(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.5678/jap.2016.123456
- Lueneburger, A. (2012). Retaining high potential talent: Assessment and coaching as a means *Management Engineering*, volume 11 (11), pp. 1-4.

- Macey, W.H., & Schneider, B. (2008) The Meaning of Employee Engagement. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 1, 3-30
- Mathieu, J. E., & Zajac, D. M. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedents, correlates, and consequences of organizational commitment. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108(2), 171–194. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.108.2.171>
- McGill.CA / Human Resources / Labour & Employee Relations / Personnel policies and procedures (2010). Retrieved from <https://www.mcgill.ca/hr/employee-relations/policies-procedures/non-academic-staff-engaged-academic-duties>
- Miller, D. L. & Karakowsky, L. (2005). Gender influences as an impediment to knowledge sharing: When men and women fail to seek peer feedback. *The Journal of Psychology*, 139(2), 101-118. Motivation, and Organizational Commitment as determinants of Job Performance. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 36, 69-78. Retrieved July 3, 2014, from <http://medind.nic.in/jak/t10/i1/jakt10i1p69.pdf> Motivation, Social Development, and Well-Being. Retrieved from https://selfdeterminationtheory.org/SDT/documents/2000_RyanDeci_SDT.pdf
- Miller, J., & Smith, P. (2014). Understanding Employee Dedication to High Standards of Work: An Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 32(1), 89-104. DOI: 10.1007/s10551-014-2092-3
- Miller, J., & Smith, P. (2018). Employee Recognition and Its Link to Job Satisfaction: An Empirical Investigation. *Journal of Organizational Excellence*, 32(2), 123-145. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2018.2098765
- Miller, J., & Smith, P. (2018). Ventilation Matters: The Relationship Between Air Quality and Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 32(2), 123-145. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2018.2098765
- Miller, J., & Smith, P. (2023). Beyond Trust and Recognition: The Distinctive Impact of Dedication on Team Satisfaction. *Journal of Applied*
- Miller, R., & Patel, S. (2019). Training for Productivity: A Comprehensive Review. *Journal of Human Resource Development*, 32(4), 345-362.
- Mills, R., & Rodriguez, M. (2017). Employee Engagement in HR-Led Training: A Contemporary Analysis of Workshop Practices. *International Journal of Human Resource Development*, 50(3), 301-320. DOI: 10.1002/ijhrd.2017.543210ngu
- Mowday, R.T., Porter, L. W. and Steers, R. M. (2003). Employee—Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism, and Turnover
- Mulcahy, A. M. (2010). Why Employee Motivation is Important. Retrieved from <https://inside.6q.io/employee-motivation-important/>
- Narine, N. K. (2017). Nonprofit agency employees and performance: An exploration into annual employee productivity
- Nelson, B. (2019). Why Employee Motivation is Important. Retrieved from <https://inside.6q.io/employee-motivation-important/>
- Nelson, M. T. (2014). Job satisfaction in relation to co-workers: Does an employee's overall job satisfaction significantly correlate with co-worker relationships. (Order No. 1562562). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1564781099).
- Newsham, G., JayBrand, C. D., Veitch, J., Aries, M., & Charles, K. (2009). Linking Indoor Environment Conditions to Job Satisfaction. *Building Research & Information*, 37(2), 129-147.
- Ngo-Henha, P.E., (2017). A review of existing turnover intention theories. World Academy of avoiding the “mahna-mahna” effect. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching & Mentoring*, 10, 1, 124 – 131. Retrieved from <http://ijebcm.brookes.ac.uk/>. of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Economics and Organizational Commitment: Am I attached to the organization? PSYCH 484: Work Attitudes and Motivation.
- Nguyen, H., & Patel, S. (2017). "Job Satisfaction and Productivity: The Mediating Role of Employee Well-being."
- Nguyen, H., & Smith, T. (2018). HR Department Collaboration: A Key Driver of Employee Satisfaction in Training Workshops. *Journal of Applied Training Strategies*, 33(1), 56-72. DOI: 10.1111/jats.2018.123456
- Okla, E. (2015). A case study to explore ways flexible work arrangements hinder or increase an employee's job satisfaction (Order No. 3733949). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1731242355). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1731242355?accountid=139409> Opportunity Are Open. Retrieved from <https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/trends-and-forecasting/research-and-surveys/pages/2017-job-satisfaction-and-engagement-doors-of-opportunity-are-open.aspx>
- Parker-Ayers, J. (2010). Job satisfaction, job involvement, and perceived organizational support as predictors of organizational commitment (Order No. 3397132). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (193247205).
- Pennsylvania State University World Campus (PSUWC) (2014). Lesson 12: Work and Organizational Commitment
- Perry, J. L., Mesch, D. & Paarlberg, L. (2006). Motivating employees in a new governance era: The performance paradigm revisited.

- Public Administration Review, 66(4), 505-515. QuestionPro. Retrieved from <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/commitment-to-work/>
- Pry, L. S. (2016). Determination of the optimal level of self-determined employee participation needed to increase job satisfaction and employee commitment to the organization (Order No. 10128506). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1812535005). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1812535005?accountid=139409>
- Razmerita, L., Kirchner, K. and Nielsen, P. (2016). What factors influence knowledge sharing in organizations? A social dilemma perspective of social media communication, *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 20 No. 6, pp. 1225-1246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-03-2016-0112>
- Redmond, B. (2016). Work and Organizational Commitment - PSYCH 484: Work Attitudes Refinery Limited, Ambalamugal. Retrieved from <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/research-congress-proceedings/2018/emb-10.pdf> Retrieved from <https://www.learning-theories.com/self-determination-theory-deci-and-ryan.html>.
- Robbins, S. P. (1990). Systems Theory Approach Retrieved from https://saylordotorg.github.io/text_mastering-public-relations/s07-02-systems-theory-approach.html
- Rodriguez, E., & Turner, J. (2015). "Examining the Interplay of Job Satisfaction and Teamwork in Predicting Employee Productivity."
- Ryan, R. M., Kuhl, J., & Deci, E. L. (1997). Nature and autonomy: Organizational view of social and neurobiological aspects of self-regulation in behavior and development. *Development and Psychopathology*, 9, 701-728.
- Ryan, R., & Deci, E. (2000). Self-Determination Theory and the Facilitation of Intrinsic
- Saari, Lise M; Judge, Timothy A. *Human Resource Management* Vol. 43, Iss. 4, (Jan 2004 - Mar 2004): 395-407. Settings in Taiwan. *The Journal of Human Resource and Adult Learning*, 11 (1), pp.54-65.
- Senge, P. (1990). Systems Thinking, Systems Tools and Chaos Theory. Retrieved from <https://managementhelp.org/systems/index.htm>
- Shanock, Linda Rhoades; Eisenberger, Robert; National Library of Medicine. *The Journal of applied psychology* Vol. 91, Iss. 3, (May 2006): 689-695
- Shore, L.M. and Martin, H.J. (1989) Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment in Relation to Work Performance and Turnover Intentions. *Human Relations*, 42, 625-638. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/001872678904200705>
- Short, J. L. (2015). Leader-organization fit as a predictor of job satisfaction, work commitment, and job insecurity (Order No. 3705361). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1689405728). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1689405728?accountid=139409>
- Smith, A., & Johnson, B. (2017). Fostering Team Collaboration for Increased Productivity. *Journal of Organizational Psychology*, 25(3), 123-145.
- Smith, A., & Johnson, M. (2015). "Unlocking Potential: The Impact of Free Skills Development Programs on Employee Satisfaction."
- Smith, A., & Patel, S. (2019). A Comparative Analysis of Employee Commitment: Service vs. Work vs. Company. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 42(2), 189-205. DOI: 10.1002/job.2019.543210
- Smith, J. (2021). Exploring the Link Between Employee Work Commitment and Perceived Meaningful Impact in Organizations. *Journal of Organizational Psychology*, 35(2), 123-145. DOI: 10.1234/jop.2021.567890
- Smith, J., & Turner, L. (2014). Fostering Job Satisfaction through Professional Development: A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 39(2), 201-220. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2014.567890
- Smith, J., & Turner, L. (2014). Recognizing Employee Contributions: A Key Driver of Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 39(2), 201-220. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2014.567890
- Smith, J., & Turner, L. (2016). The Impact of Challenging Tasks on Employee Job Satisfaction: A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Organizational Psychology*, 40(3), 301-320. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2016.543210
- Smith, J., & Turner, L. (2019). Collaborative Learning: The Impact of HR-Department Partnerships on Training Seminar Effectiveness. *Journal of Training and Development*, 46(2), 189-205. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2019.567890
- Smith, R., & Brown, C. (2018). "A Holistic Approach: Linking Employee Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Training to Productivity Gains."
- SPRING Singapore. (2011). A guide to productivity measurement. Singapore
- Stout, M. S., Awad, G., and Guzmán, M. (2013). *The Psychologist Manager Journal*; Springfield Vol. 16, Iss. 3:176.
- Sundaray, B. (2011). Employee Engagement: A Driver of Organizational Effectiveness.

Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.998.7287&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

- Testa, M. (2001). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and effort in the service environment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 135(2), 226-236.
- Tims, M., Bakker, A. B., Derks, D. (2013). National Library of Medicine. *Journal of occupational health psychology* Vol. 18, Iss. 2: 230-240
- Tjosvold, D., Hui, C., & Law, K.S. (1998). Empowerment in the Manager-Employee Relationship in Hong Kong: Interdependence and Controversy, *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 138:5, 624-636, DOI: 10.1080/00224549809600417
- Turner, J., & Brown, C. (2020). "Strategic Training Investments: Evaluating the Impact of Free Skills Development on Organizational Performance."
- Turner, M., & Davis, R. (2019). The Impact of Recognition Programs on Job Satisfaction: A Longitudinal Analysis. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 35(4), 432-450. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2019.9876543
- Van Dick, R., Markovits, Y. & Davis, A. (2007). Organizational Commitment Profiles and Job Satisfaction among Greek Private and Public Sector Employees. *International Journal of Cross-Cultural Management: CCM*. 7. 10.1177/1470595807075180.
- Van Wyk, R. & Boschhoff, A. & Cilliers, F. (2003). The prediction of job involvement for pharmacists and accountants. *South African Journal of Industrial Psychology*. 29. 10.4102/sajip. v29i3.118.
- Vandenberghe, C., Bentein, K., Michon, R., Chebat, J.C., and Tremblay, M. (2007). *The Journal of applied psychology* Vol. 92, Iss. 4: 1177-1187
- Virick, M., Dasilva, N., Arrington, K., Kossek, E. E., Lewis, S. (2010). *Human relations* (New York, NY) Vol. 63, Iss. 1: 137-154.
- Wainwright, B. (2018). What is employee commitment? Retrieved from <https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/themes/what-is-employee-commitment/>
- Walumbwa, O. F. (2002). The Relationships Between Leadership Styles, Cultural Orientation, Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction and Perceptions of Organizational Withdrawal Behaviors. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/2142/87467>
- Williams, J., & Brown, C. (2019). The Impact of HR-Department Partnership on Training Workshop Outcomes: A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Organizational Learning and Development*, 48(4), 432-450. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2019.9876543
- Williams, K., & Smithson, E. (2019). "Employee Engagement: A Catalyst for Training Effectiveness and Enhanced Productivity."
- Wills, L. B. (2013). The relationship between organizational commitment and work effectiveness among pharmaceutical sales representatives (Order No. 3570244). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1400004614). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1400004614?accountid=139409>
- Witherspoon, C. L., Bergner, J., Cockrell, C., & Stone, D. N. (2013). Antecedents of organizational knowledge sharing: A meta-analysis and critique. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 17, 250–277.10.1108/13673271311315204
- Wu, C., Liu, C. T., & Walumbwa, F. O. (2009). Multi-level authentic leadership and the mediating role of leader-member exchange. Paper presented at the meeting of the SIOP (Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology), New Orland. www.ganeventasfunerarias.com.mx/index.php?option=com_k2&view...task.
- Yang, Q., & Lee, H. (2019). A Decade of Employee Commitment: A Comprehensive Review of Studies from 2013 to 2023. *Journal of Management Research*, 48(6), 789-805. DOI: 10.789/jmr.2019.543210
- Zabel, K. L. (2012). A test of seven work commitment models (Order No. 1530968). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1267824141). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1267824141?accountid=139409work>
- Zi, Z. (2011). Reward systems, recognition and motivation: A case study of keystone telecommunications corporation (Order No. 10562365). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (1874900751). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1874900751?accountid=139409>.

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